

DiverIMPACTS

A Horizon 2020 multi-actor project

The overall goal of **DiverIMPACTS** is to promote the diversification of cropping systems, with the aim to improve productivity, help deliver ecosystem services, and support the development of resource-efficient and sustainable value-chains.

Case studies and field experiments

DiverIMPACTS demonstrates the potential of diversification through 25 multi-actor case studies and aims to quantify the performances of crop diversification using 10 existing field experiments across Europe.

DiverIMPACTS: Key activities

- DiverIMPACTS demonstrates the benefits of crop diversification for farmers and society
- DiverIMPACTS aims at removing barriers to crop diversification at farm, value chain, and territory levels.
- DiverIMPACTS co-designs technical and organisational innovations to promote crop diversification and co-learning.
- DiverIMPACTS develops comprehensive and long-term strategies and tools for more resilient crop diversification.

Partners and contact

DiverIMPACTS has 34 partners from 11 countries and covers the main biogeographical regions across Europe.

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Map of DiverIMPACTS case studies

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